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PHARMACIST ROLE IN PHARMACOTHERAPY COUNSELING, A NECESSARY OBLIGATION – OUR EXPERIENCE

¹Mr.Sci.Ph.Agron Thaqi; ²Prof Assoc. Dr. Armend Vuçiterna MD,PhD;
³Mr.Ph. Albulena Dragusha; ⁴ Mr.Ph Krenare Shehu;
⁵Dr Kosovare Dragusha; ⁶Dr. Ali Venhari

¹University Clinical Centre of Kosovo Department in Pharmacy

²University Clinical Center of Kosovo Pediatric Clinic

³University Clinical Center of Kosovo Biochemistry Clinic

⁴University Clinical Center of Kosovo Oncology Clinic

⁵University Clinical Center of Kosovo Dentistry Clinic

⁶University Clinical Center of Kosovo of Dentistry Clinic

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Abstract

In this paper we wanted to show that how much value and important role has got a pharmacologist making consultations and showing consideration towards his/her duty, thus by making it being recognized for the health care team, further taking the responsibilities on pharmacotherapy results and life of the patients.

Keywords: Pharmacist role in pharmacotherapy counseling, a necessary obligation, etc

Introduction

Based on the continuous changes on the health care system, in recent years the role of pharmacologist has undergone some changes as well. Pharmacologist's responsibilities nowadays are based on the resolution of the World Health Organization. The role of pharmacologists on supporting the new strategy on medicament usage highlights the duty of pharmacologist on counseling how to use the medicaments and their active role on disease prevention and health upkeep. This way the pharmacologist is a necessary member of health care team and carries a part of responsibility on pharmacotherapy results and life quality of the patients. His role should be clearly assigned on the health care system and on the national policy on medicament usage equally in every country. As a health care professional he should provide the securest and most effective pathway usage of medicaments that doctors prescribe.

Study Aim

is to show our experience, value and give important role to the pharmacologist on pharmacology consultation as a necessary duty, making it so the pharmacologist to be an important part of the health care team, and taking the responsibilities on pharmacotherapy results and life of the patients.

Methodology

Study group was made of 50 pharmacies, who had present a pharmacologist. In a prospective way, on dynamic follow we have analyzed all the pharmacies where the pharmacologist was present. The work was done during the period February- June 2015.

Results

Based on the results we came to a conclusion that: we have achieved a higher health care of patients on the presence of pharmacologist, on pharmacotherapy counseling where the pharmacologist plays a big and necessary part on pharmacotherapy.

Conclusions

Based on our experience, we recommend that every pharmacologist should play an active part on disease prevention and health upkeep.

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